

Research Article

Epidemiological Assessment of Tuberculosis Prevalence across Age and Gender Groups in Ahoada, Rivers State, Nigeria

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Article Info

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Prevalence, Age Distribution, Gender Differences.

Received: 06.11.2025;

Accepted: 20.12.2025;

Published: 31.12.2025

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Abstract

Background: Despite medical, scientific and public health advancements, Tuberculosis (TB) remains a serious global health challenge in low income and middle-income countries, including Nigeria, where disease burden differs across demographic groups. Understanding age and gender-related patterns of TB occurrence is important for targeted strategic control measures. This study assessed the prevalence of TB across age and gender groups in Ahoada, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was carried out among patients diagnosed of TB at Ahoada Zonal Hospital. A total of 4,490 sputum samples were collected and analyzed using Ziehl-Neelsen staining for acid-fast bacilli and GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay for Mycobacterium tuberculosis detection. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square test, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: From the 4,490 of participants examined, TB prevalence increased progressively with age, peaking in age ≥ 51 years (23.3%). The lowest prevalence was obtained in infants aged 0-5 years (0.4%). Overall, the highest prevalence (67.8%) occurred in females when compared to males (32.2%). Although in age 6-9 and 10-14 years, higher prevalence was observed in the males, females predominated in the adult age groups. Age and gender were significantly associated with TB occurrence ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: This study revealed a nuanced role of gender and age in the prevalence of TB in Ahoada, with the overall higher prevalence recorded in adult females, though a higher prevalence was found in male children aged 6-9 and 10-14 years only, indicating the need for future research to explain underlying mechanisms driving gender and age disparities in the prevalence of TB.

1. Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the oldest and persistent infectious disease that affects human [1, 2]. This highly infectious disease is caused by the bacterium “*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*” which has attacked human populations for many years, thus shaping and influencing the economy and societies [3, 4]. Despite medical, scientific and public health advancements, TB remains a serious global health challenge, that affects millions of people globally, per annum [5, 6]. The mechanism of TB transmission is primarily via inhalation of airborne droplets that

contain *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, which an infected individual expel through coughing or sneezing [1, 7–9]. Thus, close human contact and shared airspace facilitates the spread of the disease, in addition to over crowdedness, lack of ventilation, and weakened immune systems, which further exacerbate the risk of TB transmission [10]. Immune weakening conditions, such as malnutrition, HIV/AIDS, and diabetes, increase susceptibility to TB significantly [11, 12]. Furthermore, socioeconomic determinants such as poverty, inadequate access to health care and homelessness contribute to the TB burden, especially in vulnerable populations [13]

Various challenges have hindered the efforts in controlling TB, including inadequate healthcare infrastructure, inaccessibility to diagnostics and treatment, lack of funding, and social stigmatization associated with TB infection [14].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 10 million people developed TB in 2019, with approximately 1.4 million deaths attributed to the disease [14]. The country Nigeria is included among the 30 high burden TB countries [15], with an estimated TB incidence of 322 per 100 000 population of which only 15% of the total burden of the disease in the country being notified in 2015 according to WHO [16]. The burden of TB is not distributed evenly across societies and populations. Certain regions carry a disproportionate share of the disease burden, accompanied with under-reported and undiagnosed cases. There is paucity of evidence-based data on the prevalence of TB specifically in Ahoada, Nigeria. This study is urgently needed due to the lack of recent epidemiological data on age and gender specific patterns of TB prevalence in Ahoada, and aims at providing recent locality-based prevalence estimate of TB, providing age and gender specific TB burden estimate in Ahoada, Nigeria.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study design and Sampling method

A cross-sectional study was conducted at Ahoada Zonal Hospital between April and October 2025. All consecutive patients presenting to the DOTS clinic with a confirmed diagnosis of tuberculosis during the study period were included using a total population sampling approach. All consenting patients accessing care during the study period were included in the study after obtaining ethical approval from Rivers State Ministry of Health Ethics Committee.

2.2. Participants' Eligibility

All individuals diagnosed with tuberculosis and presenting to Ahoada Zonal Hospital during the study period were considered eligible for inclusion in the study. Eligibility was limited to patients of all ages who submitted sputum specimens for laboratory analysis using the GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay or Ziehl–Neelsen staining, and who provided informed consent to participate. For children, assent was obtained alongside parental or guardian consent. Only patients with complete clinical and laboratory records were included to ensure the accuracy of data analysis. Individuals were excluded if their sputum samples were inadequate, contaminated, or produced invalid results despite repeat testing, as well as those undergoing treatment for non-tuberculous mycobacterial infections. Patients who declined consent or whose clinical information could not be verified were also excluded from participation. This approach ensured that the study population was clearly defined, ethically enrolled, and representative of the TB cases managed at the hospital during the study period.

2.3. Sample collection method

A total of 4,490 sputum samples were obtained from patients with diagnosed cases of tuberculosis in accordance with standard GeneXpert laboratory procedures [17]. One sputum sample per participant was collected and processed following WHO-recommended GeneXpert MTB/RIF diagnostic procedures, which require only a single specimen for reliable TB detection

2.4. Laboratory Methods

Microscopic Identification of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

The identification of Acid-fast bacilli (AFB) in sputum samples was carried out using the Ziehl-Neelsen (ZN) staining method per NTBLCP guidelines [18]. In the procedure, direct smears of each participating patient's sputum were made on a sterile glass slide, air-dried, fixed, and stained using 1% carbol fuchsin and with heat respectively. This was followed by decolorization of the slides using 3% acid alcohol and counterstaining with methylene blue (0.1%). In order to ensure quality assurance, positive and negative controls were included with each batch of analysis. The slides were examined microscopically under a fluorescence microscope.

Genotypic Detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Bacteria Isolates

The genotypic detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* from the sputum samples was done using the GeneXpert MTB/RIF platform following the manufacturer's instructions and according to Emorinken et al [19]. Briefly, using the provided sample reagent, samples were homogenized, vortexed, and incubated for 15 minutes under the room temperature. Two milliliters aliquot of each processed sample was thereafter transferred to a test cartridge and loaded into the GeneXpert machine. Results (MTb detected, not detected, or invalid) were automatically generated by the system following approximately 90 minutes duration, based on the analysis of fluorescent signals.

2.5. Statistical analysis

The data was entered and analysed using IBM SPSS statistics® version 24.0 for Windows. Descriptive statistics were presented as frequency and percentages. The association between variables was analysed using Pearson's Chi-square. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

3. Results

Figure 1: Gender-based Prevalence of TB Patients in Ahoada

The distribution of tuberculosis (TB) cases in Ahoada as shown in Figure 1 reveals a higher prevalence among females (67.8%) compared to males (32.2%). This indicates that TB infection was more common in females within the study population.

Figure 2: Age-based Prevalence of TB Patients in Ahoada

The age-based distribution of tuberculosis (TB) cases in Ahoada shows a gradual increase in prevalence with advancing age. The lowest prevalence (0.4%) was observed among children aged 0–5 years, while the highest prevalence (23.3%) occurred among individuals aged 51

years and above. A sharp rise in TB prevalence is noticeable from the 31–35 years age group onward, indicating that TB is more common among middle-aged and older adults.

Table 1: Age and Sex Distribution of Tuberculosis (TB) Cases among the Examined Population

Age group (yrs)	Total Examined n (%)	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Chi-square (X^2)	DF	p-value	Remark
0-5	17 (0.4)	8 (47.0)	9 (53.0)				
6-9	59 (1.3)	31 (52.5)	28 (47.5)				
10-14	70 (1.6)	46 (65.7)	24 (34.3)				
15-20	110 (2.4)	27 (24.5)	83 (75.5)				
20-25	209 (4.7)	23 (11.0)	186 (88.9)				
26-30	345 (7.7)	50 (14.5)	295 (85.5)				
31-35	492 (10.9)	113 (23.0)	379 (77.0)				
36-40	722 (16.1)	194 (26.9)	528 (73.1)				
41-45	799 (17.8)	267 (33.4)	532 (66.6)				
46-50	619 (13.8)	264 (42.6)	355 (57.4)				
≥ 51	1048 (23.3)	425 (40.6)	623 (59.4)				
Total	4490 (100)	1448 (32.2)	3042 (67.8)	237.8	10	<0.001	Statistically significant

A total of 4,490 individuals were examined for tuberculosis (TB). The distribution across age groups indicates that TB detection increased with age, peaking among individuals aged ≥ 51 years (23.3%), followed by those aged 41–45 years (17.8%) and 36–40 years (16.1%). The lowest occurrence was observed in children aged 0–5 years (0.4%), suggesting that TB was more common among adults than in younger age groups. Sex distribution revealed that females (67.8%) constituted a higher proportion of TB-positive cases compared to males (32.2%). The chi-square test ($X^2 = 237.8$, $df = 10$, $p < 0.001$) shows a statistically significant association between age and sex distribution of TB cases among the examined population.

4. Discussion

The findings of this study reveal important age- and gender-related differences in the prevalence of tuberculosis (TB) in Ahoada, Nigeria. The low prevalence recorded among children, particularly those aged 0–5 years, aligns with established evidence on childhood immunity and TB protection. In Nigeria, routine administration of the Bacillus Calmette–Guérin (BCG) vaccine at birth provides substantial protection against severe forms of TB in early life, contributing to the low detection of active TB among children. In addition, the concept of the “wonder years,” as described by Seddon et al [20], highlights a period of immunological maturation during which children tend to contain Mycobacterium tuberculosis infection more effectively than adults. The typically lower bacterial load in paediatric TB cases also reduces the likelihood of detectable disease, as noted by Carvalho and Kritski [21]. These observations are consistent with studies reporting reduced TB incidence in children and adolescents compared to older adults [22, 23].

The sharp rise in TB prevalence from middle age onward, peaking in individuals aged ≥ 51 years, echoes global patterns reported in similar settings [24–26]. TB in older adults is strongly influenced by immunosenescence, the gradual weakening of immune function with age which increases susceptibility to both new infections and reactivation of latent TB [27–29]. Age-related comorbidities, diagnostic delays, and reduced mobility further contribute to the higher burden observed in this group. Older adults often experience challenges with timely access to healthcare, which may facilitate disease progression and late diagnosis.

A significant aspect of this study is the pronounced gender disparity observed. Females accounted for a much higher proportion of TB cases (67.8%) than males (32.2%). This contrasts with findings from [30–32], who generally reported higher TB burdens among males. The female predominance observed in Ahoada may reflect underlying social determinants such as limited educational attainment, socioeconomic disadvantage, and reduced access to health information and healthcare services among women, as documented by Eichener and Robbins [33, 34]. These factors may increase their vulnerability to infection or delay care-seeking.

However, an inverse pattern was observed among children aged 6–9 and 10–14 years, where males demonstrated higher TB prevalence than their female counterparts. This contradicts reports by [35, 36], who found higher TB rates among female adolescents. The male predominance in these age groups in the current study may be attributable to biological and hormonal factors influencing immune responses. Testosterone and progesterone exert immunosuppressive effects by impairing macrophage activation, potentially increasing susceptibility to TB [37–39]. During childhood and puberty, fluctuating levels of sex hormones can impact immunity and may modulate susceptibility to infectious diseases, including TB [40, 41]. The sex-specific immune differences described by Nhamoyebonde and Leslie [37] support the idea that biological variations, rather than behavioural factors alone, may explain the disparities seen in younger age groups.

Overall, the findings indicate that both age and sex significantly influence TB occurrence in Ahoada. While adult females showed the highest burden, the unique pattern seen among male children highlights the complexity of TB epidemiology and the interplay of biological, social, and environmental factors.

5. Conclusion

To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to report high prevalence of TB in females compared to males. There were gender and age differences in the incidence rates for tuberculosis, with higher rates in female infants aged 0–5 years, 15–20 years and above, when compared to age-matched males. However, the only excess in male gender was in the age groups 6–9 and 10–14 years. This indicates that both age and sex significantly influenced TB occurrence, with higher prevalence among adult females.

Recommendation

The age-related gender differences in tuberculosis prevalence observed in Ahoada, Nigeria, indicate the importance of including sex and age as biological variables when assessing the risk factors for tuberculosis.

Limitations

Our study employed a cross-sectional design involving individuals who presented to Ahoada Zonal Hospital diagnosed of TB. Hence, infected individuals not accessing health care as well as those relying on traditional treatment were not included in the study.

Article Information

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

Competing Interests: Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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